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OBSERVING THE RETURN OF DAO:
EASTERN INTERPRETATION OF SONATA OF THE SPRING

Video of presentation: <https://youtu.be/e3S4DMOorWs>

Čiurlionis is our first acquaintance with Lithuanian art. We gave him a Chinese name, 居琉璃 *Ju Liu Li*, which means “living in a world of *Liu li*”, where “*Liu li*” is a beautiful ancient colored glaze. In Chinese culture, *liuli* - colored glaze - symbolizes a separate colorful, transparent world of Bodhisattvas, different from our regular mundane world. There is also an ancient Chinese poem “彩云易散琉璃脆” “colorful clouds are easy to scatter, and colored glaze is brittle,” telling us that the preciousness of beauty often so quickly passes away. Čiurlionis’ life of art was beautiful and brittle, just like a colored glaze. His works of art for us became the gates into Lithuanian culture. In this paper, we discuss the understanding of Ju Liu Li’s *Sonata of the Spring*, which depicts the four primary elements in the universe: earth, wind, water, and fire.

Keywords: M. K. Čiurlionis, Dao, comparative aesthetics, four elements, concept of returning, world of Bodhisattvas, Laozi.

Return of Dao

When viewing paintings of Čiurlionis, we often sense an extraordinary feeling. Here, when using the English phrase “to view”, we actually mean a Chinese character 观 *guan*. In Chinese, the words 观 *guan* “to view” and 看 *kan* “to look” have distinct meanings. *Kan* “to look” means seeing in a purely physical sense, while *guan* “to view” means viewing with one’s heart, and thus through a painting carry a heart-soul conversation with the painter. We, as Chinese, don’t know that much about Lithuania’s history and culture, nor have we had enough time to thoroughly research the life of Čiurlionis, however, why does the beauty of his paintings move us so deeply? The first and most important answer that comes to mind is that his paintings are saturated with broad meaning of the universe and life. His paintings are not just abstract drawings, they have traces of reality depicted by combining images in an unexpected and very

peculiar way. It is a reality of a world or worlds that we maybe haven't imagined before, but upon seeing them we can experience and accept them as real. The cosmic feeling transcends countries and cultures, thus in Čiurlionis' paintings we find aspirations for eternity. The worlds under his brush in Buddhist terms are neither born nor destroyed 不生不灭 *bu sheng bu mie*, always there, waiting to be discovered. In traditional Chinese thought, spring is when *yang qi-energy* is in its fullness, and all ten thousand things are returning to life. According to Laozi text: "All ten thousand things arise, and I observe their return", in simple terms meaning that in spring all forms of life begin to sprout, and by observing the early sprouts one can realize the meaning of the circle of life, as well as the workings of the Dao-Path. Therefore, using Laozi's ideas about 观复 *guan fu* "observing the returning", we may approach *Sonata of the Spring* as an organic whole, and explore its meaning of the cosmos and life.

First, we can see that the *Sonata of the Spring* depicts the four major elements in the universe: earth, wind, water and fire. We associate the theme of the first painting *Allegro* with the element of earth. During the first days of spring, the breath of winter has not yet faded away, but the little willow buds have already started sprouting in the soil. The second painting *Andante* expresses the wind (or air) element, the blowing winds make windmills rotate, and the rotation of windmills starts the motion of *qi-energy*, as well as the surrounding white clouds that fill a large space of the painting. In the third *Scherzo* painting, the dominant theme is the element of water. There, fish and water plants in the water move and the fishing net cast out gives the whole painting a sense of sinking and stability. The fourth *Finale* painting expresses the element of fire. The two high towers in the picture create an association of two tall chimneys with rising smoke from fire, while colorful flags become the expression of the souls in the whole work. We regard the four pictures as an organic whole - the four elements of earth, wind, water

liuli 琉璃-in ancient China, the colored glaze is always used for symbolizing a separate colorful and transparent world of Bodhisattvas, or the Daoist immortals.

An image of a porcelain tower on a Chinese food container.

This 600 year old pagoda door at the Nanjing Museum which statues the Entrance of Buddha world by colored glaze, is the relic of the Great Bao-en Temple 大报恩寺, famous as the Oriental Porcelain Tower in Western countries.

and fire constitute a complete universe, while the willow trees, windmill, fish and souls constitute the transformation and flow of various life forms.

Secondly, the theme of life flowing in all four paintings constitutes another level of “observing the returning”. The first painting represents the beginning of life. The trees by the water convey the very beginning of life when everything seems so beautiful and perfect. The trees like musical notes sway in the wind, and the river flows down along the rock wall. The whole picture is filled with the scent of life. While gazing at this painting, one seems to be listening to the sounds of nature, as in the famous analogy of Zhuangzi called 天籁之音 *tian lai zhi yin*. In the second painting, a huge windmill is whirling high in the sky, as if the wind of the universe is causing the whole world to tremble. Rows of small windmills below respond with echoes to the windmill in the center, and the whole painting relays a sense of the vast and mighty wind of the cosmos, which is the freedom and power of life itself. Among the other three *Sonata of the Spring* paintings *Andante* with its immense windmill taking up most of the space of the painting has the strongest visual impact on a viewer. This is

The Spring Garden in the suburb of Nanjing 金陵正春园
Traditional Chinese architecture with colored glazed tile indicates a pure outer world.

not often seen in the composition of Chinese paintings. To express the power of wind, Chinese are accustomed to using large unoccupied spaces, and at the same time, the painting would be more restrained to display the magnitude of the world in comparison with the loneliness of a human being. Čiurlionis in this painting apparently is attempting to reveal a stronger force and a deeper emotion.

We find the third painting *Scherzo* as the most challenging one. Every time we look at *Scherzo*, we have an urge to take the three wooden pegs out of the painting. The wooden pegs that fell from the sky with a whistling sound break the balance between heaven and earth, as well as the balance of the picture, giving us a sense of weightlessness. More importantly, these wooden pegs made us reconsider our inherent Oriental aesthetic understanding. If those three wooden pegs are removed, then the composition of this painting becomes so Oriental and similar to some Chinese landscape paintings. We could even say that without those pegs it would be a classical painting known as “one river and two banks” with “equal and remote” composition, making the whole view calm and harmonious. The image of fish is very common in Chinese paintings, and painters often use fish to express the unbound and free spirit like in the painting *Group of Fish Playing with Algae*. However, in *Scherzo*, three wooden pegs thrown on the surface also seem to be thrown on a human heart. The net

Sonata of Spring

Observing the Returning

Group of Fish Playing in Algae, Southern Song Dynasty
(春溪水族)

Ba Da Shan Ren, Qing Dynasty
(1644–1911), Fish

catches the fish, just like the net catches all of us. The beauty of life is accompanied by the tragic experience of life. Even more interesting is that there are a few fish outside the net, and these fish are calm and are not startled or afraid. The contrast between different groups of fish seems to indicate that our physical bodies are confined within the fishing net, while our soul-spirits freely roam outside the net. It could be also said that the existence of those uncaught fish implies the transcendence over the net, the restraint and the physical world. This kind of spirit is so much like the Chinese calligrapher's Bada Shanren fish with rolling eyes. Both Čiurlionis and Bada Shanren's fish drift apart from this mundane shore of life.

The last work *Finale* under the theme of fire expresses the return of the body (Planet Earth) and the transcendence of the spirit (colorful flags). What attracts us most about this painting is those colorful winding flags. It reminds us of the words from a poem written by painter Ni Zan of the Yuan Dynasty (1271–1368): "Throughout the world the one who travels to the other shore

Dai Jin, Ming Dynasty (1368–1644), *Returning Boat in Storm* 风雨归舟图

finds out I am the carrying empty boat” (The empty boat that carries souls to the other shore). In the eyes of Chinese painters, a painting can be used to liberate oneself and others by passing to the other shore, that is, by leading people to a world beyond, to the place where souls reside. Just like the colorful flags in this painting, it takes us out of worldly glory and mundane shackles to another world, to the land of soul and spirit. What’s interesting is that Čiurlionis, similar to Chinese painters, chooses vast space and faraway horizons to express the other shore. For example, Qian Xuan’s *Mountain Dwelling* painting connects the world on this shore with the one on the other shore with a bridge. By crossing the bridge, we can leave the mundane world and reach the other sacred world. The similarities with the colorful flags of Čiurlionis are so evident. Through these four works of the *Sonata of the Spring*, Čiurlionis expresses life from the beginning to thriving, from fetters to freedom, from the return of the physical body to the transcendence of the spirit. The *Sonata of the Spring* constitutes a cycle of life, as well as the “observing of return”.

Therefore, Laozi says: “All the ten thousand things arise and I observe their return (to their original state)”, and then continues “They arise and bloom, but eventually all return to their root. Returning to the root is called the state of stillness, and stillness we call returning to Dao.” All things repeat the cycles of life, every new cycle starts from Dao, and eventually ends in stillness and space. Stillness and space are concepts of Eastern Philosophy based on observation and experience. The observance of returning implies the recurrent cycles of life, and stillness and space are closely related to cosmic eternity. We think that these ideas of “observing the return” with “stillness and space” can facilitate a stronger

Qian Xuan, *Mountain Dwelling*, 山居图

and more vivid realization of a cosmic feeling and life consciousness depicted in *Sonata of the Spring*, as well as help to discover the value of Čiurlionis' art that transcends time and cultural boundaries.

Sun Min, Zhan Bin

DAO SUGRĮŽIMO STEBĖJIMAS: PAVASARIO SONATOS
RYTŲ INTERPRETACIJA

Santrauka

Čiurlionis – pirmoji mūsų pažintis su Lietuvos menu. Mes jam suteikėme kiniską vardą 居琉璃 Ju Liu Li, kuris reiškia „gyvenimas Liu li pasaulyje“. „Liu li“ yra graži senovinė spalvota glazūra. Kinų kultūroje liuli – spalvota glazūra – simbolizuoja spalvingą ir skaidrų Bodhisatvų pasaulį, kuris skiriasi nuo mūsų įprasto žemiško pasaulio. Yra toks senovės kinų eilėraštis „彩云易散琉璃脆“ „spalvingus debesis lengva išsklaidyti, o spalvota glazūra yra trapi“, kuris pasakoja, kad grožis yra trapus ir trumpalaikis. Čiurlionio meninis gyvenimas taip pat buvo gražus ir trapus, kaip ši spalvota glazūra. Jo meno kūriniai mums tapo vartais į Lietuvos kultūrą. Šiame darbe aptariame Ju Liu Li (Čiurlionio) pavasario sonatą, kurioje vaizduojami keturi pagrindiniai visatos elementai: žemė, vėjas, vanduo ir ugnis, supratimą.

Raktažodžiai: M. K. Čiurlionis, Dao, lyginamoji estetika, keturi elementai, grįžimo samprata, Bodhisatvų pasaulis, Laodzi.